

STUDENT KNOWLEDGE MANAGEMENT AS A MAIN ELEMENT OF EDUCATION QUALITY ASSESSMENT

Doctoral student Bukhara State University

Rasulova Zilola Durdimurotovna

Annotation: The article talks about the modern methods, form, methods and tools of the student knowledge assessment system. The content of the criteria for evaluating students' knowledge is explained.

Key words: Activity, knowledge, pedagogical skills, objective assessment, Haqqani, fair assessment, oral, written and test control types.

Introduction. One of the most sensitive aspects of the reforms implemented in the higher education system of our Republic today is the evaluation of students' knowledge. That is, the process of organizing teaching in the higher education system and the system of evaluating the knowledge of students receiving education do not meet today's requirements, and accordingly, the modern assessment of the activity, knowledge and pedagogical skills of professors and teachers the lack of a system has a negative impact on the quality of education.

It means an objective assessment of both theoretical and practical aspects of the student's knowledge gained during the semester on the subjects included in the educational program. Objective assessment, regardless of its form and duration, must correctly and fairly record the student's learning level. An honest and fair evaluation system is one of the pillars of the higher education system, therefore, establishing and improving the objective evaluation system around the world is one of the main tasks of universities and other higher education institutions. In order to increase the objective assessment of the student's knowledge and to determine the quality of the given lesson, the final evaluations can be carried out using tests that

include other professors or general course materials, through a computer system of rating evaluation.

The main part. Students' mastery of subjects in each semester is evaluated according to each evaluation type: 5 (excellent), 4 (good), 3 (satisfactory) and 2 (unsatisfactory).

5, 4 and 3 grades are positive. In the evaluation, the number and the text are interpreted the same. Various forms of assessment of the student's knowledge of science are usually used: oral assessment, written assessment, test-based assessment and rating system.

1. The good aspects of oral supervision and evaluation:

- the professor-teacher communicates directly with the student; there is an opportunity to ask additional questions to determine the student's knowledge in depth;

- oral response encourages the student to practice speaking and think actively. A well-prepared student can demonstrate his knowledge and additional learning while giving an oral answer. During direct questioning, some doubts that had arisen in the teacher about the student's learning are eliminated.

2. Advantages of written assessment:

- the written answer is a documentary evidence that the student has mastered the learning material;

- is a practice for the student to express his thoughts on paper; written control conducted by experts provides an opportunity to objectively assess the student's knowledge.

3. Serious defects specific to the oral and written assessment system:

- there are more signs of subjectivity in the assessment of the student's knowledge, the assessment is often compared to other students, in which case the assessment may be reduced or increased. Examinees can score different marks for a single oral answer or a single written assignment;

– in the exam, the student answers 3-4 questions on the ticket, and the grade is given for the fact that he knows the content of the entire curriculum
www.ziyouz.com library; - the five-point rating scale does not allow to clearly define the differences between the levels of knowledge acquisition;

– oral and written exams cannot provide an objective, accurate and reasonable assessment of the quality of knowledge acquisition;

– it takes a lot of time to ask orally, as well as to check written work;

– it is difficult to use a computer for oral and written control, they cannot be automated.

4. The advantages of assessment with a pedagogical test tool:

– a well-structured pedagogical test is an objective assessment tool for accurate measurement of the quality and level of a student's knowledge acquisition, the result of which does not depend on the supervisor-assessor;

– pedagogical test can fully cover the content of the educational material of the science program, when measuring the educational result by the test method, it is the same for all students, based on a predetermined scale, a clear and correct assessment can be made. cried;

– it is convenient to use the technical means of education in the assessment by test, this method allows to monitor the knowledge of all students by spending relatively little time and effort on a certain educational material or an entire subject;

– assessment by pedagogical test method can be automated by computer.

When evaluating students' knowledge, the professor-teacher faces the question What should be evaluated? Pedagogical technology gives the answer to this question: “The level of achieving the goals and tasks of teaching and learning the subject.” In this case, it is necessary to connect the general goal with the activity of the teacher (such as teaching, explaining, telling, demonstrating), and the tasks should be expressed in connection with the learning activity of the student, that is, the educational task.

To evaluate the quality of education, the following are used as sources of information:

education statistics; intermediate and final certification; monitoring works; sociological research; school staff reports; participation in classes and extracurricular activities. Internal system of evaluation of the quality of education.

The internal system of education quality assessment is aimed at solving the following tasks:

– systematic monitoring and analysis of the system in the educational system in order to make rational and timely management decisions aimed at improving the quality of educational activities and educational results;

– to maximize the effect of incompleteness and inaccuracy of information on the quality of education both at the stage of planning educational results and at the stage of evaluating the effectiveness of educational activities to achieve the appropriate quality of education destroy.

Subjectivity of knowledge assessment.

It is known that there is a lack of methods of monitoring the knowledge system. Often the assessment of the subject, the course or its parts is carried out individually examines, often secondary elements may not reflect the mastery of knowledge, skills and skills in the form of its assimilation.

Developmental principles of assessment. The most important principles of management of student performance are:

- ✓ objectivity;
- ✓ regularly;
- ✓ visual (openness)

The analysis of pedagogical tests on mastering the educational material at different levels shows that the volume of controlled knowledge, their

systematicity, gradually moving from checking the memorization and recovery of information to the reproductive level of mastering, and then to the levels of productive thinking. the ability to distinguish important areas, the ability to apply knowledge in practice will increase.

Conclusion. Taking into account the complexity of the integral concept of quality of education, a systematic approach is needed to study it, which allows to consider the problem as a whole, that is, to identify the factors influencing the problem; determine the degree of influence of these factors on the problem and on each other; it is appropriate to make a decision taking into account these effects and interactions. Understanding the different meanings of quality is a prerequisite for understanding educational quality management.

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